
REVIEW OF MOST USED URBAN GROWTH MODELS

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ABSTRACT

Smart urban growth management is a planning and management approach that seeks to promote sustainable development and quality of life in urban areas. It involves a range of strategies and practices that aim to balance economic growth, social equity, and environmental sustainability, while ensuring that urban areas remain livable and resilient over the long term. Planning and zoning: Effective land use planning and zoning can help guide growth and development in ways that support community goals and values, such as preserving open space, promoting affordable housing, and encouraging mixed-use development. Transportation planning: Smart urban growth management also involves transportation planning that prioritizes walking, cycling, and public transit, and reduces dependence on single-occupancy vehicles. This can reduce traffic congestion, improve air quality, and enhance community connectivity. Environmental protection: Smart urban growth management seeks to protect and enhance natural resources, such as waterways, wetlands, and green spaces, and reduce the environmental impact of development. Community engagement: Effective community engagement is essential for ensuring that urban growth management strategies reflect the needs and priorities of residents, businesses, and other stakeholders.

Overall, smart urban growth management is a comprehensive and collaborative approach that seeks to balance the economic, social, and environmental needs of urban areas, while ensuring that they remain livable and sustainable for generations to come.

Keywords: Urban Areas, Planning, Development, Management, Transportation

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of smart urban growth has evolved over time in response to changing urbanization trends, environmental concerns, and technological advances (Aburas, 2016).

In the mid-20th century, many cities were characterized by rapid suburbanization and sprawl, with development patterns driven by the automobile and the desire for larger homes and yards. This approach to growth often resulted in fragmented communities, traffic congestion, and a lack of access to public transportation and green space (Allen et al., 1978).

In the 1970s and 1980s, the concept of smart growth emerged as a response to these challenges, with a focus on promoting compact, walkable communities that balance economic, social, and environmental objectives. Smart growth principles emphasized the need for mixed-use development, transit-oriented development, and the preservation of open space (Brueckner, 1980).

In the 1990s and 2000s, the concept of sustainable development gained prominence, with a focus on promoting development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This approach emphasized the importance of environmental sustainability, social equity, and economic vitality (Capozza & Helsley, 1989).

In recent years, the concept of smart urban growth has evolved further to incorporate new technologies and data-driven approaches (Tobler, 1970). This has led to the emergence of concepts such as the "smart city," which emphasizes the use of technology to improve urban infrastructure, public services, and quality of life. Smart city approaches can include the use of sensors to monitor traffic and air quality, the use of data to improve public transportation and emergency response, and the deployment of renewable energy and energy efficiency technologies (Black & Henderson, 1999).

Overall, the evolution of the smart urban growth paradigm reflects a growing recognition of the need to balance economic, social, and environmental objectives in urban development, and the role that technology can play in achieving these goals.

Smart urban growth management involves a range of tools and techniques that can help cities and communities achieve sustainable and equitable growth. Some of these tools include:

1. **Comprehensive planning:** A comprehensive plan is a long-term vision for a city or region that outlines goals, policies, and strategies for managing growth and development. It can provide a framework for decision-making and help guide zoning, land use, and transportation policies.
2. **Zoning and land use regulations:** Zoning and land use regulations can help guide growth and development in ways that support community goals and values. They can also ensure that development is consistent with environmental and public health standards.
3. **According to Duranton & Turner (2012), Transit-oriented development:** Transit-oriented development (TOD) is a planning approach that focuses on creating compact, mixed-use development around transit stations. TOD can reduce dependence on cars, increase access to public transportation, and promote walkable communities.
4. **Green infrastructure:** Green infrastructure is a network of natural and semi-natural systems that provide environmental, social, and economic benefits. Examples of green infrastructure include parks, green roofs, and bioswales. Green infrastructure can help manage stormwater, reduce the urban heat island effect, and provide habitat for wildlife.
5. **Community engagement:** Community engagement is essential for ensuring that urban growth management strategies reflect the needs and priorities of residents, businesses, and other stakeholders. Techniques for community engagement can include public meetings, surveys, focus groups, and online platforms (Arnott, 19080).

6. Performance-based zoning: Performance-based zoning is a regulatory approach that sets goals for desired outcomes, such as reducing traffic congestion or increasing energy efficiency, and allows developers to choose the most appropriate strategies for achieving those goals (Kazemzadeh-Zow, et al. 2017).

Overall, smart urban growth management tools aim to balance economic, social, and environmental needs while ensuring that urban areas remain livable, sustainable, and resilient over the long term.

2. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Most of the urban expansion started with growth in demand for more housing for migrating populations in the cities (Mayer & Somerville, 2000). Urban growth models are mathematical and computational tools used to simulate and project the growth and development of urban areas over time. These models can help planners and policymakers understand the drivers of urban growth, forecast future growth patterns, and evaluate the potential impacts of different growth scenarios (García, 2010). Zhou et al. (2019) had done a high-resolution global urban growth projection based on multiple applications of the SLEUTH urban growth model.

Table 1. Comparative table of popular urban growth models:

Model Name	Year Developed	Approach	Key Features	Advantages	Disadvantages
Cellular Automata (CA)	1970s	Simulation	Model land use change as an iterative process based on neighborhood interactions	Captures spatial patterns and interactions	Limited ability to incorporate socio-economic factors
Agent-Based Model (ABM)	1990s	Simulation	Model individual agents and their decision-making processes to simulate land use change	Flexible and dynamic modeling of complex systems	High computational demand
Markov Chain Model	1980s	Probability	Probability-based model that predicts the probability of a cell changing from one land use category to another	Simple and efficient	Assumes the future is independent of the past
Logistic Regression Model	1970s	Statistical	Model the probability of land use change based on socio-economic and biophysical variables	Easy to interpret and implement	Assumes a linear relationship between variables
Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR)	1990s	Statistical	Model the spatially varying relationship between variables and land use change	Captures local spatial variations	Sensitive to the choice of kernel function and bandwidth
UrbanSim	2000s	Integrated	Integrated model that combines land use, transportation, and environmental planning	Considers multiple factors and feedbacks	Data-intensive and computationally demanding

Source: Compiled by author

Note: This table is not exhaustive and there may be other urban growth models not included here. Additionally, the advantages and disadvantages listed are not meant to be comprehensive and may vary depending on the specific application of each model.

Spatial modelling for urban growth saw a tremendous increase in application due to popularity of the use of remote sensing and geographic information systems (GIS) and other counter aided analytical tools (Musa et al., 2017). Nong & Du (2011) studied urban growth pattern modeling using a logistic regression model which was good research work for others to learn from. Silva & Clarke (2002) used calibration of the SLEUTH urban growth model for Lisbon and Porto, Portugal for predicting the urban growth. Thapa & Murayama (2011) used urban growth modeling of Kathmandu metropolitan region, Nepal and this work is worth referring to for understanding the growth of metropolitan regions.

Fig. 1. Different forms of Urban Growth Models, author

There are several types of urban growth models, each with its own strengths and limitations:

1. Cellular automata models: Cellular automata models simulate the growth of urban areas by dividing space into a grid of cells and using rules to determine how each cell changes over time. This approach can capture the complex interactions between land use, transportation, and other factors, but may be computationally intensive and may not capture social or economic factors (Long et al., 2009).

Cellular automata models are a type of mathematical and computational model used to simulate the growth and development of urban areas over time. These models divide space into a grid of cells, each of which can take on one of several possible states (e.g., urban, agricultural, or natural land cover). The state of each cell is determined by a set of rules that specify how the state of the cell is influenced by the states of its neighboring cells (Hu & Lo, 2007).

The rules governing the state transitions can be based on a range of factors, such as land use policies, transportation infrastructure, population growth, and environmental conditions. For example, a rule might specify that if a cell is adjacent to a road, it is more likely to become urbanized over time. Over many iterations of the model, the cells change state based on these rules, producing a simulation of urban growth and change (Huang et al., 2010).

Cellular automata models can be used to explore different scenarios for urban growth and to evaluate the potential impacts of different policies and interventions. They can also be used

to identify areas that are at risk of future development, to identify areas that are suitable for conservation or restoration, and to forecast future growth patterns (Maithani, 2009).

However, cellular automata models have some limitations. Makse et al. (1998) explained that it is computationally intensive and requires a large amount of data to develop accurate models. They may also oversimplify the complexity of urban systems and may not capture the social and economic factors that influence urban growth. As a result, cellular automata models should be used in conjunction with other planning and management tools to ensure that urban growth is sustainable, equitable, and resilient over the long term (Wilson et al., 2002).

2. Agent-based models: Agent-based models simulate the behavior of individual agents, such as households or firms, and how their interactions shape urban growth. This approach can capture the social and economic factors that influence urban growth, but may require detailed data on individual behavior and may not capture macro-level trends.

Agent-based models (ABMs) are a type of mathematical and computational model used to simulate the growth and development of urban areas over time. ABMs focus on the behavior of individual agents, such as households, businesses, and government agencies, and how their interactions shape urban growth.

In ABMs, each agent is assigned a set of attributes, such as income, preferences, and location. The agents are then programmed to make decisions based on these attributes and a set of rules that govern their behavior. For example, a household might choose to move to a new neighborhood based on its income, housing preferences, and proximity to employment opportunities (Triantakonstantis & Mountrakis, 2012).

As agents interact with each other, they can influence each other's behavior and the overall growth of the urban area. For example, if a large number of households choose to move to a particular neighborhood, this can attract new businesses and amenities to the area, which can in turn attract even more households.

ABMs can be used to explore different scenarios for urban growth and to evaluate the potential impacts of different policies and interventions. They can also be used to identify areas that are at risk of future development, to identify areas that are suitable for conservation or restoration, and to forecast future growth patterns.

ABMs have some advantages over other types of urban growth models. They can capture the social and economic factors that influence urban growth, and can simulate the emergence of complex patterns of behavior and interactions between agents. However, ABMs can be computationally intensive and require a large amount of data to develop accurate models. They may also oversimplify the complexity of urban systems and may not capture macro-level trends. As a result, ABMs should be used in conjunction with other planning and management tools to ensure that urban growth is sustainable, equitable, and resilient over the long term.

3. Regression models: Regression models use statistical techniques to identify the relationships between urban growth and various factors, such as population, income, and land use policies. This approach can be useful for forecasting future growth trends, but may not capture the complexity of urban systems.

Regression models are a type of statistical model used to identify the relationships between urban growth and various factors, such as population, income, land use policies, and environmental conditions. These models use historical data on urban growth and other variables to develop a predictive model of future growth patterns.

Regression models typically involve identifying a dependent variable, such as the rate of urban growth, and a set of independent variables, such as population, income, and land use policies.

The model then uses statistical techniques to estimate the relationships between the dependent variable and the independent variables, and to predict future growth patterns based on changes in these variables.

Regression models can be used to explore different scenarios for urban growth and to evaluate the potential impacts of different policies and interventions. They can also be used to forecast future growth patterns and to identify areas that are at risk of future development.

Regression models have some advantages over other types of urban growth models. They can capture the complexity of urban systems and can be used to identify the relative importance of different factors in driving urban growth. They can also be relatively simple and easy to understand and can provide policymakers and planners with a clear understanding of the potential impacts of different policies and interventions.

However, regression models also have some limitations. They assume that the relationships between the dependent and independent variables are linear, and may not capture the nonlinear relationships that can exist in urban systems. They also rely on historical data, which may not be representative of future growth patterns, and may not capture the complex interactions and feedback loops that can exist in urban systems. As a result, regression models should be used in conjunction with other planning and management tools to ensure that urban growth is sustainable, equitable, and resilient over the long term.

4. Land-use transport interaction models: Land-use transport interaction models simulate the interactions between land use patterns and transportation systems, and how these interactions shape urban growth. This approach can capture the interdependence between land use and transportation, but may not capture other factors that influence urban growth (Robson, 2006).

Land-use transport interaction models (LUTI models) are a type of mathematical and computational model used to simulate the interactions between land use and transportation systems in urban areas. These models are used to forecast the impacts of transportation infrastructure and land use policies on urban growth, transportation demand, and environmental outcomes.

LUTI models typically use a combination of spatial and econometric techniques to simulate the interactions between land use and transportation systems. They use data on land use patterns, transportation networks, demographic characteristics, and environmental conditions to simulate how changes in transportation infrastructure and land use policies will affect travel behavior, accessibility, and urban growth.

LUTI models can be used to explore different scenarios for urban growth and to evaluate the potential impacts of different policies and interventions. For example, they can be used to evaluate the impacts of new transportation infrastructure, such as highways or transit systems, on urban growth and travel behavior. They can also be used to evaluate the impacts of land use policies, such as zoning regulations or development incentives, on urban growth and accessibility.

LUTI models have some advantages over other types of urban growth models. They can capture the complex interactions between land use and transportation systems and can be used to evaluate the potential impacts of policies and interventions on both systems. They can also be used to evaluate the impacts of policies and interventions on environmental outcomes, such as air quality and greenhouse gas emissions.

However, LUTI models also have some limitations. They can be computationally intensive and require a large amount of data to develop accurate models. They may also oversimplify the complexity of urban systems and may not capture the social and economic factors that influence urban growth.

As a result, LUTI models should be used in conjunction with other planning and management tools to ensure that urban growth is sustainable, equitable, and resilient over the long term.

Overall, urban growth models are valuable tools for understanding and managing urban growth, but they are not without limitations. To be effective, these models must be based on accurate and up-to-date data, and must be used in conjunction with other planning and management tools to ensure that urban growth is sustainable, equitable, and resilient over the long term.

There are several different types of urban growth models, each with their own strengths and weaknesses. A comparative study of these models can help to identify the most appropriate models for different applications and to evaluate the strengths and limitations of each approach.

One important distinction among urban growth models is between statistical models and simulation models. Statistical models, such as regression models, use historical data to identify relationships between urban growth and other factors. Simulation models, such as cellular automata and agent-based models, simulate the dynamic processes of urban growth and can be used to evaluate the impacts of different policies and interventions. Among statistical models, regression models have the advantage of simplicity and transparency. They can provide a clear understanding of the factors driving urban growth and can be used to predict future growth patterns. However, they may not capture the complexity and nonlinear relationships that exist in urban systems. Simulation models, on the other hand, can capture the complexity of urban systems and can be used to evaluate the impacts of different policies and interventions. However, they require a large amount of data and computational power, and may oversimplify the social and economic factors that influence urban growth.

Ward et al. (2002) explained cellular automata models have been widely used in urban growth modeling, particularly in the context of land use change. They have the advantage of simplicity and transparency, and can be used to simulate the dynamic processes of urban growth. However, they may not capture the complexity of urban systems and may oversimplify the social and economic factors that influence urban growth. Agent-based models have also been widely used in urban growth modeling, particularly in the context of transportation and land use interactions. They have the advantage of capturing the complexity of urban systems and can be used to evaluate the impacts of policies and interventions on both land use and transportation systems. However, they require a large amount of data and computational power, and may oversimplify the social and economic factors that influence urban growth.

Overall, a comparative study of different urban growth models suggests that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to modeling urban growth. Each approach has its own strengths and weaknesses, and the choice of approach will depend on the specific application and research questions. A combination of different models may be needed to capture the complexity of urban systems and to evaluate the impacts of policies and interventions on urban growth and sustainability.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, urban growth modeling is a complex and dynamic process that requires a range of different approaches to capture the complexity of urban systems and to evaluate the impacts of policies and interventions. Each of the urban growth models we have discussed - including statistical models, simulation models such as cellular automata and agent-based models, and land-use transport interaction models - has its own strengths and limitations.

Statistical models, such as regression models, provide a simple and transparent approach to understanding the factors driving urban growth and can be used to predict future growth patterns. However, they may not capture the complexity and nonlinear relationships that exist in urban systems.

Simulation models, such as cellular automata and agent-based models, can capture the complexity of urban systems and can be used to evaluate the impacts of different policies and interventions. However, they require a large amount of data and computational power, and may oversimplify the social and economic factors that influence urban growth.

Land-use transport interaction models can be used to simulate the interactions between land use and transportation systems in urban areas and evaluate the potential impacts of different policies and interventions on urban growth, transportation demand, and environmental outcomes. However, these models may oversimplify the complexity of urban systems and may not capture the social and economic factors that influence urban growth.

Overall, a combination of different urban growth models may be needed to capture the complexity of urban systems and to evaluate the impacts of policies and interventions on urban growth and sustainability. It is important to carefully consider the strengths and limitations of each model and to use them in conjunction with other planning and management tools to ensure that urban growth is sustainable, equitable, and resilient over the long term.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Author has no conflict of interest in the publication of this research paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aburas, M. M., Ho, Y. M., Ramli, M. F., & Ash'aari, Z. H. (2016). The simulation and prediction of spatio-temporal urban growth trends using cellular automata models: A review. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 52, 380-389.
- [2] Allen, P. M., & Sanglier, M. (1978). Dynamic models of urban growth. *Journal of Social and Biological Structures*, 1(3), 265-280.
- [3] Arnott, R. J. (1980). A simple urban growth model with durable housing. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 10(1), 53-76.
- [4] Black, D., & Henderson, V. (1999). A theory of urban growth. *Journal of political economy*, 107(2), 252-284.
- [5] Brueckner, J. K. (1980). A vintage model of urban growth. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 8(3), 389-402.
- [6] Capozza, D. R., & Helsley, R. W. (1989). The fundamentals of land prices and urban growth. *Journal of urban economics*, 26(3), 295-306.
- [7] Durantón, G., & Turner, M. A. (2012). Urban growth and transportation. *Review of Economic Studies*, 79(4), 1407-1440.
- [8] García, M. (2010). The breakdown of the Spanish urban growth model: Social and territorial effects of the global crisis. *International Journal of urban and regional research*, 34(4), 967-980.
- [9] Hu, Z., & Lo, C. P. (2007). Modeling urban growth in Atlanta using logistic regression. *Computers, environment and urban systems*, 31(6), 667-688.
- [10] Huang, B., Xie, C., & Tay, R. (2010). Support vector machines for urban growth modeling. *Geoinformatica*, 14, 83-99.
- [11] Kazemzadeh-Zow, A., Zanganeh Shahraki, S., Salvati, L., & Samani, N. N. (2017). A spatial zoning approach to calibrate and validate urban growth models. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 31(4), 763-782.
- [12] Long, Y., Mao, Q., & Dang, A. (2009). Beijing urban development model: Urban growth analysis and simulation. *Tsinghua Science and Technology*, 14(6), 782-794.

- [13] Maithani, S. (2009). A neural network based urban growth model of an Indian city. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, 37, 363-376.
- [14] Makse, H. A., Andrade, J. S., Batty, M., Havlin, S., & Stanley, H. E. (1998). Modeling urban growth patterns with correlated percolation. *Physical Review E*, 58(6), 7054.
- [15] Makse, H. A., Havlin, S., & Stanley, H. E. (1995). Modelling urban growth patterns. *Nature*, 377(6550), 608-612.
- [16] Mayer, C. J., & Somerville, C. T. (2000). Residential construction: Using the urban growth model to estimate housing supply. *Journal of urban economics*, 48(1), 85-109.
- [17] Musa, S. I., Hashim, M., & Reba, M. N. M. (2017). A review of geospatial-based urban growth models and modelling initiatives. *Geocarto International*, 32(8), 813-833.
- [18] Nong, Y., & Du, Q. (2011). Urban growth pattern modeling using logistic regression. *Geospatial Information Science*, 14(1), 62-67.
- [19] Robson, B. T. (2006). *Urban growth: an approach* (Vol. 9). Routledge.
- [20] Sharma, S. N. (2014). Urban forms in planning and design. *International Journal of Research*, 1(1), 7-16.
- [21] Sharma, S. N. (2014). *Participatory Planning in Plan Preparation*. BookCountry.
- [22] Silva, E. A., & Clarke, K. C. (2002). Calibration of the SLEUTH urban growth model for Lisbon and Porto, Portugal. *Computers, environment and urban systems*, 26(6), 525-552.
- [23] Thapa, R. B., & Murayama, Y. (2011). Urban growth modeling of Kathmandu metropolitan region, Nepal. *Computers, Environment and urban systems*, 35(1), 25-34.
- [24] Tobler, W. R. (1970). A computer movie simulating urban growth in the Detroit region. *Economic geography*, 46(sup1), 234-240.
- [25] Triantakostas, D., & Mountrakis, G. (2012). Urban growth prediction: a review of computational models and human perceptions.
- [26] Ward, D. P., Murray, A. T., & Phinn, S. R. (2000). A stochastically constrained cellular model of urban growth. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 24(6), 539-558.
- [27] Wilson, E. H., Hurd, J. D., Civco, D. L., Prisloe, M. P., & Arnold, C. (2003). Development of a geospatial model to quantify, describe and map urban growth. *Remote sensing of environment*, 86(3), 275-285.
- [28] Zhou, Y., Varquez, A. C., & Kanda, M. (2019). High-resolution global urban growth projection based on multiple applications of the SLEUTH urban growth model. *Scientific data*, 6(1), 34.